

Exploring OpenSearch deployment in Kubernetes

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AUTHOR(S):

Cristobal Gimenez Devis

SUPERVISOR(S):

Sokratis Papadopoulos

Luis Pigueiras

PROJECT SPECIFICATION

We are currently deploying OpenSearch using puppet on bare metal and have developed an ecosystem of code and operations around it. In this project we want to explore the standard way of deploying and operating OpenSearch: Kubernetes.

Firstly, we will create Kubernetes clusters using the CERN IT Kubernetes service and then explore two ways of deploying OpenSearch there: with and without the OpenSearch Kubernetes operator.

We will then perform all kinds of operations in our Kubernetes-hosted OpenSearch clusters, like cluster upgrades, scaling and failures and compare the experience of using the operator or not.

Another part of the project refers to setting up GitOps using ArgoCD and performing a monitoring mockup using Prometheus and Grafana.

Finally, benchmarking has to be performed so that the actual performance of the OpenSearch clusters using different kinds of volume types is measured and compared against the current OpenSearch clusters living in bare metal.

As an outcome, a summary of the learning points, should be produced.

ABSTRACT

The OpenSearch service at CERN has been operating since 2016 on puppet-managed servers.

Currently managing 122 OpenSearch and OpenDistro clusters powered by a pool of 156 powerful physical machines running AlmaLinux 9.

In the current architecture, multiple clusters live within the same host, resources isolation (e.g., cpu, ram) is achieved on the process level and disk space is managed with LVM. This deviates from the standard OpenSearch deployment.

The objective of this project is to get familiar and explore a containerized deployment of OpenSearch using the standard Docker + Kubernetes images on the CERN IT Kubernetes Service.

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1. Introduction

In this project, we want to create a prototype deployment of the OpenSearch service in Kubernetes clusters, and explore the different features of such deployment, like performance, flexibility and simplicity of operations. For that, we will need to explore different things :

1. **Cluster creation** : First, we will see what do we need to do to create a Kubernetes cluster, and how to operate with it.
2. **Deployment** : Next, once we have our Kubernetes clusters, we have to deploy OpenSearch, we will explore two options, with the help of the community-made OpenSearch K8s operator, and with only pure Helm charts.
3. **GitOps** : Everytime we need to change something about the cluster, we would need to manually operate with it, We will explore GitOps integration to use CI/CD pipelines in order to synchronize changes automatically.
4. **Failures** : In this section, we will simulate node failures , explore what happens to the OpenSearch cluster and how does it manage itself in order to be available again.
5. **Monitoring** : After the development part, we have to monitor the cluster, in order to be on the lookout for failures and metrics. Here, we will explore how monitoring can be integrated.
6. **Benchmark tests** : We will also need to make some tests in order to check the performance of the new Kubernetes clusters and compare them to the current deployment. In this section, we will make Benchmark tests to measure performance.
7. **Scaling and upgrading** : Here, we will explore how to scale and upgrade nodes.
8. **Conclusion** : Finally, we will end the report with a summary and conclusion.

2. Cluster creation

To create Kubernetes clusters, we will use **Magnum**, which is an OpenStack service provided by the CERN IT Kubernetes team to easily create Kubernetes clusters on demand.

In our project, we want to test three different types of Kubernetes clusters :

- **Single-master cluster (all VMs)** : A simple Kubernetes cluster with one master node and three data nodes. This cluster is only a prototype and will not be used in production, since the single master is a single point of failure.
- **Multi-master cluster (all VMs)** : A Kubernetes cluster with three master nodes and three data nodes, this type of cluster is a production-like deployment, since it is more robust to failures.
- **Single-master cluster (physical machine)** : A Kubernetes cluster with one master node and three data nodes, the difference in this cluster is that the data nodes are bare metal machines rather than virtual machines. However, this was dropped early in the project since the creation of a cluster with physical machines requires extra steps, operating with them is also not as easy and some extra issues that we will see in this section.

To create a Kubernetes cluster we will use **OpenStack** in the CLI :

```
$ openstack coe cluster create <name>
```

This is the basic command to create a Kubernetes cluster. However, we also need to specify the cluster architecture and some extra configuration, we must also add some labels :

- **--cluster_template <template>** : The Kubernetes version which will run in the cluster, in our case we will use version **1.30.1-1** for single-master clusters and **1.30.1-1-multi** for multi-master clusters.
- **--keypair <keypair>** : This flag associates an RSA keypair in order to communicate with SSH to the cluster.
- **--node_count <count>** : The number of worker nodes.
- **--master_count <count>** : The number of master nodes.
- **--flavor <flavor>** : The flavor (specifications) of all the worker nodes. All the possible flavors can be seen in **OpenStack**, in our case we will use the **m2.large flavor**.
- **--master_flavor** : The flavor (specifications) of all the master nodes. All the possible flavors can be seen in **OpenStack**, in our case we will use the **m2.large flavor**.
- **--merge_labels** : This flag makes the cluster use the labels we specify in the CLI and also the default labels in **Magnum**.
- **--labels cinder_csi_enabled=<enabled>** : This flag is required in order to allow the use **CinderCSI** persistence volumes.
- **--labels monitoring_enabled=<enabled>** : This flag is required to enable monitoring in our cluster (grafana, prometheus).
- **--labels grafana_admin_passwd=<pass>** : Initial admin password for grafana dashboard (in case monitoring is enabled)
- **--labels ingress_controller=<controller>** : Type of ingress class controller, usually nginx.

Before we proceed we must note :

- The cluster template used is **1.30.1-1** or **1.30.1-1-multi**
- The keypair used is named **crgrimene**
- **CinderCSI and monitoring** are enabled, the initial grafana password is "admin" and the default ingress controller is nginx

a. Creation of single-master cluster (VMs)

To create a single-master cluster we need one master node and three worker nodes (the recommended amount is three worker nodes). For that, we use this command to create a single-master cluster :

```
$ openstack coe cluster create <name> --cluster_template 1.30.1-1 --keypair
crgrimene --node_count 3 --master_count 1 --flavor m2.large --master_flavor
m2.large --merge_labels --labels cinder_csi_enabled=true --labels
monitoring_enabled=true --labels grafana_admin_passwd=admin --labels
ingress_controller=nginx
```

b. Creation of multi-master cluster (VMs)

To create a multi-master cluster we need three master nodes and three worker nodes (the recommended amounts are three master nodes in different availability zones and three worker nodes). For that, we use this command to create a multi-master cluster :

```
$ openstack coe cluster create <name> --cluster_template 1.30.1-1-multi --keypair
crgrimene --node_count 3 --master_count 3 --flavor m2.large --master_flavor
m2.large --merge_labels --labels cinder_csi_enabled=true --labels
monitoring_enabled=true --labels grafana_admin_passwd=admin --labels
ingress_controller=nginx
```


c. Creation of single-master cluster (PHYSICAL MACHINES)

To create a single-master cluster with physical machine we need to first, create a cluster with virtual machines, and then add the physical machines after the creation :

```
$ openstack coe cluster create <name> --cluster_template 1.30.1-1 --keypair
crgimene --node_count 1 --master_count 1 --flavor m2.large --master_flavor
m2.large --merge_labels --labels cinder_csi_enabled=true --labels
monitoring_enabled=true --labels grafana_admin_passwd=admin --labels
ingress_controller=nginx
```

After creating the cluster, we have one master and one worker node (in this example), now, we have to add the physical machines, in order to do that, we create a new nodegroup in the cluster with the physical machine flavor.

```
$ openstack coe nodegroup create <name_of_cluster> <name_of_nodegroup>
--node_count 1 --flavor p1.dl8822089.S513-V-IP413 --role <role> --merge_labels
--labels cinder_csi_enabled=true --labels heat_container_agent_tag=train-
stable-6
```

Here, the flag `--role` defines the role of the node inside the cluster and `p1.dl8822089.S513-V-IP413` is the flavor of the physical machines.

Once this is done, we have our physical machines in the cluster, however, there is one more issue (at least, currently) , the physical machines are not assigned an internal IP, thus making operating with the machine hard, while some things (e.g. ingress) are practically not supported.

Due to these issues, working with physical machines was dropped, and the focus became only VMs.

3. Deployment

Once we have our cluster setup, we must now deploy **OpenSearch** on our cluster, for that we will explore two options for the deployment :

- Using the community-made [OpenSearch Kubernetes operator](#) which simplifies a lot of common operations, and adds features for scaling, updates, draining, etc.
- Using [Helm Charts](#) only, in order to not have one extra dependency and for better default GitOps monitoring.

a. Deployment with operator

In order to deploy OpenSearch with the Kubernetes operator, first, we need to install the operator in our cluster. For that, we will install and deploy the Helm chart of the operator.

First, we install the repository containing the chart :

```
$ helm repo add opensearch-operator https://opensearch-
project.github.io/opensearch-k8s-operator
```

Then, we install the operator:

```
$ helm install opensearch-operator opensearch-operator/opensearch-operator
```


Once the operator is deployed, we must deploy the clusters. The operator defines a *CustomResourceDefinition* in Kubernetes in order to deploy the clusters. For that, we must make a .yaml file which will contain the specification of both the OpenSearch nodes and the OpenSearch Dashboards. In that file, we must specify several attributes:

- **version:** The version of both the OpenSearch Docker image, and the version of the OpenSearch Dashboards.
- **Memory and cpu** requests for each pod.
- **replicas:** The number of OpenSearch nodes
- **diskSize:** Disk space for each of the OpenSearch nodes.
- **roles:** The roles of the cluster nodes, can be “cluster_manager”, or “data”.
- **storageClass:** The PVC storage class, if CinderCSI is enabled it can be used.

An example of this file can be seen in [gitlab](#).

b. Deployment with Helm

To deploy OpenSearch with only Helm charts, we must install the repositories of both the OpenSearch Helm chart and the OpenSearch Dashboards chart

```
$ helm repo add opensearch
https://opensearch-project.github.io/helm-charts
```

This installs the repositories of the both the clusters and the Dashboards, now what is left is to deploy them :

```
$ helm install opensearch-clusters opensearch/opensearch -f values.yaml
```

```
$ helm install opensearch-dashboards opensearch/opensearch-Dashboards
```

The **values.yaml** file used when deploying the cluster is a Helm value file, just like when deploying the clusters with the operator we must specify :

- **version:** The version of both the OpenSearch Docker image, and the version of the OpenSearch Dashboards.
- **Memory and cpu** requests for each pod.
- **replicas:** The number of OpenSearch nodes
- **diskSize:** Disk space for each of the OpenSearch nodes.
- **roles:** The roles of the cluster nodes, can be “cluster_manager”, or “data”.
- **storageClass:** The PVC storage class, if CinderCSI is enabled it can be used.

Note : Starting from OpenSearch version 2.12.0 forward, it is required to setup an initial admin password, as an environment variable, if we use that version on our clusters we must also specify a password like in this example value file in [gitlab](#). In the case of the operator, there is currently a GitHub [issue](#) open because it's not possible to set this password, which means that we can only use versions lower than 2.12.0.

c. Access OpenSearch Dashboards

Once we have our OpenSearch cluster deployed and running we want to access the OpenSearch Dashboards in order to view metrics, use the developer tools, etc. We have two ways of accessing the Dashboards.

Port-forward

The OpenSearch Dashboards pod exposes the port 5601 to communicate with it, so, that is the port we must port-forward. Then, we can either port-forward the pod directly, or the service which redirects to the pod.

```
$ kubectl port-forward opensearch-dashboards 5601
```

```
$ kubectl port-forward svc/opensearch-service-dashboards 5601
```

Then, we can access <https://localhost:5601> to view the Dashboards.

Create an Ingress

Another way of viewing the Dashboards is creating an Ingress to it. An Ingress is a Kubernetes object that manages external access to the services in a cluster, by exposing a HTTP and HTTPS port

So, we can make an Ingress which redirects to the service Dashboards which will communicate with the pod running the OpenSearch Dashboards. To deploy an Ingress we must:

- Change the **Magnum** values to allow a **nginx** ingress.
- Tag one of the worker nodes as the Ingress.
- Deploy the Ingress which points to the service.

In order to create the Ingress, we need to update the namespace **kube-system** with new Helm values. We then run:

```
$ helm get values cern-magnum -n kube-system > magnum-values.yaml
```

Inside the **magnum-values.yaml** we add and delete the following:

- Delete the first line “USER-SUPPLIED VALUES”.
- Then, in the section **ingress-nginx** we add:


```

ingress-nginx:
  controller:
    watchIngressWithoutClass: true
    ingressClassResource:
      default: true
    ...
    nodeSelector:
      node-role.kubernetes.io/ingress: true
  enabled: true

```

- Finally at end of the file, we must disable traefik:

```

traefik:
  enabled: false

```

After all of this is done we upgrade the values with Helm :

```

$ helm -n kube-system upgrade cern-magnum
oci://registry.cern.ch/kubernetes/charts/cern-magnum --version 0.16.0
-f magnum-values.yaml

```

Once the upgrade is completed we must do one extra step, the ingress controller lives in a *DaemonSet*, but, the *nodeSelector* tags of this controller are still wrong, we must edit the *.yaml* of the controller in the following way:

```

$ kubectl edit ds/cern-magnum-ingress-nginx-controller -n kube-system

```

We navigate to the *nodeSelector* section and we replace the line “*role: ingress*”:

```

nodeSelector:
  kubernetes.io/os: linux
  role: ingress

```

```

nodeSelector:
  kubernetes.io/os: linux
  node-role.kubernetes.io/ingress: true

```

Once this is completed, we tag one of the worker nodes as ingress, and deploy the Ingress:

```

$ kubectl label node kubevm-rwjIntoq3oso-node-0
node-role.kubernetes.io/ingress=true

```

```

$ kubectl apply -f dashboard-ingress.yaml

```

An example of an Ingress can be seen in [gitlab](#).

Finally, we must add the host we defined in our Ingress to CERN DNS:

```

$ openstack server set --property landb-alias=<alias>--load-1- kubevm-
rwjIntoq3oso-node-0

```


Where `<alias>` refers to the name of the URL we want to define. After a while, the DNS will update and then we can navigate to `<alias>.cern.ch` to view the Dashboards.

4. ArgoCD GitOps

To deploy our OpenSearch cluster in Kubernetes with a CI/CD pipeline we will use ArgoCD, a popular Continuous Delivery tool for Kubernetes. More specifically we will use the already made ArgoCD instance «**embargo**» provided by the ASM section.

a. Previous steps

Before adding to the instance everything related to our project, we must first make some extra steps :

- **Get the public GPG key:** Some files in the **embargo** repository must be encrypted, and they have to be encrypted with their GPG public key like specified in their [documentation](#).
- **Create a group access token:** ArgoCD is a tool that synchronizes changes made in repositories. Which means that ArgoCD must have access to such repositories, to grant it access, we must make a group access token in GitLab to allow ArgoCD to view all the changes.
- **Update .sops:** Since we will need to give ArgoCD access to our repositories, we will have to give the access token to embargo, but this token cannot be uploaded to the repository in plain text, it has to be encrypted. We will have to encrypt some files with the **embargo** public key, for that we must update the **.sops** file and add a path to the [token](#).
- **Add the token to embargo:** Once we have our token created, we must give it to ArgoCD, we make a file in which we add the group access token and then we encrypt it with sops, the result looks like [this](#).
- **Add the repository credentials:** Once we have our GitLab token created and added, we must add it to the instance, as specified in their [documentation](#) and the GitLab [documentation](#) for access tokens. The result is something like [this](#).
- **Add credential to embargo:** Next, we must add the credential to the instance so that ArgoCD knows it is there, see the result [here](#).
- **Add the source repositories:** Finally, we add the links to all the repositories from which ArgoCD will look for changes, in our case we need five links:
 - Link to repository of the Helm chart for the OpenSearch Kubernetes operator.
 - Link to repository of the Helm charts for the OpenSearch clusters and Dashboards.
 - Link to repository where the OpenSearch cluster yaml file is defined (used with the operator).
 - Link to repository of the value files for the OpenSearch cluster with operator.
 - Link to repository of the value files for the OpenSearch Helm charts.

The result is then something like [this](#).

With this, we have configured ArgoCD to access some repositories, and look for changes there. Now the second part is left, which is to add the cluster references so that Argo can apply those changes.

b. Add cluster references

As we said earlier, we have to set the cluster references in order for Argo to apply any changes. For this, we make the following steps:

- **Create a service account for ArgoCD inside the cluster:** In order for ArgoCD to make changes in the cluster, it must have administrator permissions, so, we create a service account for ArgoCD:

```
$ kubectl -n kube-system create sa argoadmin
```

```
$ kubectl create clusterrolebinding argoadmin --clusterrole=cluster-admin --serviceaccount=kube-system:argoadmin
```

Then, we apply a secret just as it specified in the [embargo documentation](#).

- **Adding credentials of the cluster to ArgoCD:** Now, we need to get the secret token and the certificate in order to let ArgoCD communicate with our cluster:

```
$ kubectl -n kube-system get secret/argoadmin-secret -o yaml
```

The certificate will be used exactly as it shows in the output. The token, however, must be introduced to ArgoCD base64 decoded. We put our token in a txt file and run

```
$ cat token.txt | base64 -d
```

Then, we add the IP direction of the cluster, the token, and the certificate in a file just as it says on the [documentation](#) and then encrypt it with sops. The result looks like [this](#).

c. Deploy OpenSearch with operator (ArgoCD)

To deploy an OpenSearch cluster with the operator, we must first, deploy the operator, and the clusters. For this, we make a new yaml file which will target the repository of the Helm chart of the operator, and deploy it, just like [this](#).

Then, to deploy the cluster, we make another yaml file which will take the value files defined in our own repositories and use them to deploy the cluster, see the file [here](#).

d. Deploy OpenSearch without operator (ArgoCD)

To deploy an OpenSearch cluster without the operator, we only have to make one yaml file, which will point to the Helm repository of the OpenSearch cluster chart, and also it will take our own value files defined in our repositories, see the file [here](#).

5. Node failures

We tested what happens when one of the worker nodes in our Kubernetes clusters fails taking into account the presence of the Kubernetes operator and only the Helm charts.

To simulate a node failure, we shutdown a VM instance in OpenStack, and monitor what happens to the data internally. In this example, we shutdown the node number 1 and see how the data is handled.

SHARDS	NODE
8	openk8s-nodes-0
8	openk8s-nodes-1
8	openk8s-nodes-2

SHARDS	NODE
8	openk8s-nodes-0
8	openk8s-nodes-2
4	UNASSIGNED

SHARDS	NODE
10	openk8s-nodes-0
10	openk8s-nodes-2

We can see that when the node fails, the data is redistributed to other nodes and no data is lost. During this time, the cluster health is yellow and there is no downtime during this process.

We must note that there is no behavioral difference between having the operator or not. And also, that a new OpenSearch pod is created automatically, but a new Kubernetes node is not created.

Also, if our cluster is using the Kubernetes operator, ArgoCD has no visibility on node failures, however when using only the Helm chart, ArgoCD can see if a node failed.

6. Monitoring

In order to be on the lookout for failures, and get useful metrics of our cluster, we have to monitor it. In our project, we did a mock up with [Prometheus](#) and [Grafana](#) to export metrics and visualize them.

For this, inside our OpenSearch cluster, we must add and do a few things:

- **Add a monitoring secret for Prometheus:** In order for Prometheus to scrape metrics, it needs to access the OpenSearch cluster, we add a [secret.yaml](#) file which holds the initial username and password that was set when we deployed the OpenSearch clusters.
- **Add a service monitor for Grafana and Prometheus:** Grafana visualizes the metrics exported by Prometheus, but must tell Prometheus where to look for them. In order to do this, we define a [service monitor](#) in which we specify the port and path to scrape the metrics.

Once all of this is done, we can port-forward or create an Ingress to Prometheus and Grafana. In the case of Grafana we use a community made dashboard which includes many metrics, it can be found [here](#).

7. Benchmark tests

Next, we want to measure the performance of the OpenSearch clusters in Kubernetes compared to the Puppet clusters. For this we use [OpenSearch Benchmark](#), a python library which performs all tests, and computes many metrics.

To get our results, we create an isolated physical machine instance, in which we install OpenSearch Benchmark. Then we create an isolated Kubernetes cluster and we deploy OpenSearch in it. After that, we make an Ingress to the service which redirects to the three nodes (for load balancing).

Finally we try different cluster configurations (vRAM, vCPUs, StorageClasses) and different workloads (Big5 – 100GB, HTTP logs – 34 Gb).

After the tests we create four Dashboards in order to visualize the results:

- (Tiny, Http)
- (Tiny, Big5)
- (Medium, Http)
- (Medium, Big5)

The results can be seen in the [perfmon](#) cluster.

8. Scaling and upgrading

Finally, we explore how scaling and upgrading can be performed in our cluster.

When scaling a cluster, we can either scale up (add more resources) or scale out (add more nodes). Now, let's see how this upgrade can be done and if there's any difference between the operator and the charts.

When upgrading, we change the version of Docker Image of OpenSearch, but the way Kubernetes works is that the pods using the image must be terminated and new pods with the upgraded image must be created.

a. Scaling and upgrading with operator

With the operator all of these resources and features can be changed :

- **Replicas:** If we want to add a new pod, the operator adds a new one easily.
- **Memory and CPU:** The operator also allows an easy change of resources by just changing the yaml file.
- **DiskSize:** The most useful feature of the operator is that you can change the disk size of each pod in the yaml file, and the operator takes care of creating new PVCs and attaching them to the running pods automatically.
- **Version:** The operator performs a *RollingUpdate* of the cluster when upgrading the OpenSearch version, while upgrading, each pod is killed one by one and the operator waits to proceed with the update each time until the cluster health is green.

b. Scaling and upgrading without operator

- **Replicas:** If we want to add a new pod, the Helm chart allows to change the value file.
- **Memory and CPU:** The process of adding more resources it's not straightforward, to add more resources the StatefulSet in which the pods live has to be edited manually.
- **DiskSize:** Cannot be scaled with only the Helm charts, it has to be done manually.
- **Version:** The Helm chart also performs a *RollingUpdate* of the pods.

9. Conclusion

In this project, we have created a prototype deployment of OpenSearch inside Kubernetes clusters and explored ways of deployment like with the Kubernetes operator and with Helm charts. In summary we can conclude that:

- **Kubernetes** offers better flexibility compared with the current **Puppet** deployment
- **OpenSearch** clusters using **io2** and **io3** show good performance.
- The **OpenSearch** operator eases common operations like scaling, handling failures and upgrading.
- **ArgoCD** provides an easy monitored way of configuring **OpenSearch** clusters in **Kubernetes**.
- **Kubernetes** deployment provides easy integration with **Prometheus**, thus aligning with **MONIT** service.

